

POTENTIAL STRATEGIES TO OVERCOME THE CHALLENGES IN BLENDED LEARNING MODELS IN EFL/ESL CONTEXTS: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS

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Abstract:

Blended learning, which combines traditional face-to-face instruction with online learning activities, has gained significant attention in the field of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) and English as a Second Language (ESL) education. (Ding, Gao and Lu, 2017). While blended learning models offer numerous advantages, they also present unique challenges that need to be addressed for effective implementation. This thesis aims to explore the challenges encountered in blended learning models in EFL/ESL contexts, identify their underlying causes, and propose potential strategies to overcome them. The research draws on a comprehensive literature review and empirical studies to provide valuable insights for EFL/ESL educators, curriculum designers, and policymakers. By analyzing the challenges faced in blended learning models in EFL/ESL contexts, this thesis aims to contribute to the existing body of knowledge in the field of language education. This thesis discusses potential strategies to address these challenges and optimize the effectiveness of blended learning.

Acknowledgement

The very first issue is technological challenges which can be tackled by ensuring access to reliable technology and internet connectivity. Schools and institutions should provide necessary resources, such as devices and internet access, to both teachers and learners. Collaboration with local communities and leveraging mobile technologies can help overcome infrastructure limitations. Rasheed, Kamsin and Abdullah (2020) suggested that offering comprehensive training programs and ongoing technical support is needed to provide technical

support and training which can enhance teachers' and learners' technological competence and confidence in navigating digital tools and platforms. Additionally, Alammary (2019) stated that by implementing contingency plans one can anticipate technological failures or disruptions and establish backup solutions, such as alternative communication channels or offline learning materials, to minimize learning interruptions. Selecting intuitive and user-friendly digital tools and platforms that facilitate seamless interaction, collaboration, and content delivery. (Garrison and Kanuka, 2004).

Next, Pedagogical challenges is the following challenge which can be solved by designing relevant and engaging learning materials. Develop well-structured online learning materials and activities that align with learning objectives, incorporate multimedia resources can foster active learning through interactive elements, simulations, and gamification techniques. In addition, promotion of communication and collaboration by incorporating synchronous and asynchronous communication channels to facilitate interaction and collaboration among learners, as well as between learners and teachers are proper ways to establish effective blended learning environment. By giving clear guidelines and instructions instructor provide learners with clear online expectations, participation, assessment criteria, and deadlines to ensure a smooth learning experience. Moreover, continuous feedbacks are important as they support to learners to address their individual needs, monitor progress, and provide guidance for improvement.

Learner Challenges are the following important problem that should not be neglected. They can be dealt by:

- a. Conducting thorough needs assessments to identify learners' digital literacy skills and provide targeted support and resources accordingly;
- b. Promoting learner autonomy by offering self-paced learning opportunities, resources, and tools that enable learners to take control of their learning journey (Garrison and Vaughan, 2008);

- c. Fostering a supportive online learning community and designing collaborative activities and promoting peer interaction to foster a supportive and inclusive online learning environment;
- d. Establishing clear and consistent communication channels for learners to seek assistance, ask questions, and receive timely responses;
- e. Regularly monitoring and evaluating learner progress through formative assessments and adapting instruction accordingly to address individual learning challenges (Law, Geng and Li, 2019).

Blended learning models offer immense potential for enhancing EFL/ESL education. By implementing the strategies discussed in this thesis, educators and policymakers can effectively tackle the challenges associated with blended learning, thus optimizing learning outcomes and ensuring a successful implementation of blended learning models in EFL/ESL contexts. Continued research and evaluation of these strategies will further contribute to the advancement of blended learning practices and their impact on language education.

Reference

1. Alammary, A. (2019). Blended learning models for introductory programming courses: A systematic review. *PLoS ONE* 14:e0221765. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0221765
2. Ding, Y., Gao, Y., and Lu, F. (2017). The development of QM-fudan higher education online course quality standards: some results and analysis. *Am. J. Distance Educ.* 31, 198–206. doi: 10.1080/08923647.2017.1301142
3. Garrison, D. R., and Kanuka, H. (2004). Blended learning: uncovering its transformative potential in higher education. *Internet High. Educ.* 7, 95–105.
4. Garrison, D. R., and Vaughan, N. D. (2008). *Blended Learning in Higher Education: Framework, Principles, and Guidelines*. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons

5. Law, K. M., Geng, S., and Li, T. (2019). Student enrollment, motivation and learning performance in a blended learning environment: the mediating effects of social, teaching, and cognitive presence. *Comput. Educ.* 136, 1–12. doi: 10.1016/j.compedu.2019.02.021

6. Rasheed, R. A., Kamsin, A., and Abdullah, N. A. (2020). Challenges in the online component of blended learning: a systematic review. *Comput. Educ.* 144:103701. doi: 10.1016/j.compedu.2019.103701